

MS32: Procedures to include national services in EOOSC

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Document Abstract

This is the accompanying document of MS32, which describes the procedures to include national services in EOOSC.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

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1 Executive summary

This document describes the guidelines for onboarding services into a catalogue, either at national or European level.

Since there are no national catalogues currently operational in the countries participating to EOSC-Pillar, this document describes the procedure to onboard services in the EOSC catalogue/marketplace only. The process is currently operated by the EOSC-hub project and is going to evolve according to the outcome of the activities carried on by the EOSC-Enhance project and, on a longer term, by the project which will be funded in the INFRAEOSC-03 call.

2 Introduction

The EOSC-Pillar project involves partners from 5 different European countries (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany and Italy) with quite different situations regarding national e-infrastructures and services as well as participation to international initiatives and projects.

In each country there are various scientific communities which are active in national and international scenarios.

This variety, and the commitments the research communities have, due to their scientific and projects activities, may impose some constraints to the operations, management and use of the services of their interest.

This is the reason why one of the first important activities of EOSC-Pillar task T7.1 has been a survey to understand what are the existing procedures at both national and international level, to onboard services into the EOSC catalogue and marketplace. By services here we mean every kind of mature¹ services, including data repositories. Onboarding datasets into a repository is currently out of scope.

The goal is to try and harmonize such procedures and guidelines with the one currently in use in the EOSC landscape, e.g. the onboarding procedure defined and managed by the EOSC-hub project. At national level there may be the need to onboard service with TRL less than 7.

The results of this activity are reported in this document.

¹This means services at Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 7 or above

3 Gathering of the relevant information

3.1 External contacts

In order to document the existing guidelines, procedures and best practices, at national and international level, relevant to services suitable to be exposed to the EOSC, as a first step we decided to exploit the activity performed in WP3 for Landscaping.

Since in the questionnaire there was no single question or set of questions who could directly provide useful insights, we asked our WP3 colleagues to extract, among the set of respondents to the “National Initiatives” survey, a sample based on answers to specific questions:

- How does or will EOSC affect your organisation and/ or your strategic plans?
 - Selected: “very much”, “somewhat”, “not very much”
- How likely is it that your organisation will contribute to EOSC?
 - Selected: “very likely” or “likely”
- How beneficial is/ will be contributing to EOSC for your organisation?
 - Selected: “very beneficial” or “somewhat beneficial”
- Some organisations have developed regulations related to their work processes, whereas other organisations have not. Has your organisation developed informal or formal regulations or publicly available policies that address the following aspects?
 - Selected: any answer, except “no regulation” and “not applicable”
- Is your organisation part of or related to another organisation which facilitates integrating your data and services into EOSC?
 - Selected: “Yes”
- Which service(s) does your organisation provide to the research community?
 - Selected: any possible answer
- Please indicate one or more of your services that you would like to become part of.
 - Selected: at least one service indicated
- Does your organisation currently have policies, procedural and/ or technical barriers that limit the expansion of your services to further user groups?
 - Selected: “Yes”
- Please describe which policies, procedural and/ or technical barriers limit the expansion of your services to further user groups
 - Free text: all contributions were sent to WP7
- We would like to know which user groups use your organisation's services. How frequently do the following groups use your services?
 - Selected: at least one group use services “frequently” or “very frequently”

According to these criteria, 387 contacts were selected and they were asked to answer the following questions:

- Are you aware of procedures and guidelines to onboard services into a common catalogue, either at national or European level? If yes, please send us a reference to them
- Are you aware of technical or operational restrictions or limitations which may apply to services when onboarding them into a catalogue? If yes, please list them

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- Are you aware of specific policies related to this? If yes, please send us a reference to them
 - Do you foresee any issue to onboard services into a common or general catalogue?
 - What does services federation mean in your context?

We informed our contacts that their responses would have been treated in anonymous and aggregated form in publications, the questionnaire would not be circulated outside of the EOSC-Pillar project and any copy of it would be deleted at the latest after 6 months: internally, we agreed with WP3 colleagues that the list which was used as input for this questionnaire would also be deleted within 6 months.

Out of the 387 contacts, 43 replied asking for more information or clarifications, and eventually 31 sent their responses.

The analysis of the responses showed that the only existing guidelines and procedures are the EOSC-hub ones. Several respondents also provided valuable additional information and comments:

- information relevant to data services and repositories which was therefore forwarded, in aggregated and anonymized form, to our WP5 colleagues
- any other information (e.g., caveats, expectations on how the “federation” should operate or expectations on the user experience when facing the EOSC portal,...) were shared within WP7, to inform future actions within the project and in the context of the numerous boards, task forces, interest groups outside of the project

The outcome of the survey was that EOSC-hub sets the standard, as far as exposing services to the EOSC portal is concerned.

In parallel to this survey, we performed an internal investigation by contacting the responsible persons for the WP6 use-cases. The outcome was that either no specific procedures exist, or they comply with EOSC-hub ones. Also in this case, we gathered additional comments on various related aspects (for example, worries about the practical governance of the catalogue and the way to present a wealth of services to the user) which were forwarded to the other WPs, specifically WP4.

4 Results: the initial guidelines and procedures to onboard services

According to the result of the surveys carried out by the T7.1 team, the initial guidelines for onboarding services into the EOSC catalogue are based on the EOSC-hub ones.

One important activity foreseen in EOSC-Pillar, specifically in task T4.4, is the definition of a model for a national catalogue of services. Although an interest for a national catalogue has been expressed by some partners of the project, an agreement on the model has not been reached yet and, more importantly for the T7.1 activities, there are no national catalogues in operation for the time being in the five countries participating to the project.

As far as we know, only in France there is a catalogue already operational but this has not been recognized as reference catalogue at national level so far.

However, the need for interoperation of national, regional or community catalogues with the central EOSC one has been expressed by several actors, including partners involved in other regional projects and this has started being discussed in various groups and task forces as well as with the EOSC-Enhance² team who is in charge for the evolution of the EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace.

So far there is agreement on the fact that two goals have to be pursued:

- technical interoperability among different catalogues in order to allow services onboarded into a national catalogue to be automatically propagated to the EOSC catalogue and vice versa
- a distributed procedure to on-board services into a catalogue

The first goal requires the definition of appropriate technologies and interfaces as well as the development of some specific tools. Discussions about this are ongoing and involve the regional projects more advanced on this, specifically the EOSC-Nordic³. The responsibility for the development of tools falls mainly on EOSC-Enhance.

With respect to the second goal, the two main ingredients are:

- a common set of mandatory criteria for onboarding, services have to be validated against. The common set should be based on the EOSC criteria which are (or have to be) derived from the Rules of Participation defined by the EOSC Governance RoP Working Group⁴
- a trustworthy environment where the validation teams at EOSC and national/regional level recognize each other and services validated either at EOSC or national regional level are considered validated by the other party.

The implementation of this scenario requires a lot of work and will take quite some time to produce a tangible outcome.

² <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/eosc-enhance>

³ <https://www.eosc-nordic.eu/>

⁴ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/rules-participation-working-group>

In addition, currently it is not possible to on-board data and other research products, such as software, publications and so on, into the catalogue, but the need for this has been expressed by several actors, including the WP5 team, and it will be considered for a (hopefully) near future.

For the time being, therefore, the EOSC-hub procedure has to be followed.

This procedure, known as Service Provider Onboarding, is documented in a wiki page⁵ of the EOSC-hub project and it is shown in the following picture

It consists of several steps:

1. the Service Provider submits the request to EOSC-hub through a form in the EOSC Portal.
2. the EOSC-hub team fills in a Service Description Template⁶ (SDT) according to the information received and checks that the information is complete
3. as soon as the SDT is complete and ready, it is passed to the Validation team which assesses the compliance of the information provided to the onboarding criteria⁷
4. once a service has been validated, it is passed to the Publishing team which publishes the services into the EOSC catalogue as well as in the EOSC Marketplace if needed.

Only services at TRL 7 or above are accepted into the catalogue while TRL 8 or above is mandatory for the Marketplace.

Services are grouped into various categories as shown in the following picture.

⁵ <https://wiki.eosc-hub.eu/display/EOSC/Service+Provider+Documentation>

⁶ the EOSC-hub SDT has been defined taking into account various inputs, including the template defined within the eInfraCentral project

⁷ <https://wiki.eosc-hub.eu/display/EOSC/Criteria+for+possible+inclusion+in+the+EOSC+Service+Portfolio>

The following table provides some additional information about the service categories.

Level-1	1-Line description	Level-2
Sharing & Discovery	Services to search and discover data, publications, tools and other resources useful for your research	Applications repository
		Software repository
		Data discovery & access
Processing & Analysis	Software, platforms, tools, analytics and end-user applications offered-as-a-service or deployed-on-demand also specialised by discipline or research domain	Analytics
		Science gateway
		Forecast modelling
Compute	Services to access virtual machines, containers and job processing to support your general computing needs	Job execution
		Virtual machine management
		Container management
		Workload management
		Orchestration
Storage	Service to use storage for your data	Online
Data Management	Service to manage your data	Federation
		Persistent identifier
		Discovery
		Access
		Preservation
		Publishing
		Annotation
		Preservation
		Confidentiality
Distribution		
Networking	Ultra-fast connectivity and ubiquitous access to eInfrastructures' resources and services you need	
Training & Support	Grow your research knowledge and skills with specialised trainings or seek dedicated professional support for a wide range of scientific disciplines	Service management
		Data management

	and research activities	
Security and Operations	Services to integrate identity management, authorisation and other security services to comply with policies and regulations or access services to support the operations of your infrastructures and services	Identity and access management

A service provider willing to propose a candidate service has to fill in a form⁸ on the EOSC portal.

⁸ <https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/becomeAProvider>

5 Future work and conclusions

The onboarding procedure described in the previous section will be updated according to the outcome of:

- the new rules of participation which are being defined by the EOSC Governance RoP working group
- a new set of criteria derived from them
- the outcome of the work EOSC-Enhance is doing
- the outcome of the regional projects.

With regards to EOSC-Enhance, a new version of the Service Description Template, which will be called “Profile”, is going to be released in June 2020 and the EOSC-hub onboarding procedure will be updated accordingly.

However, this new version is still related to services only; the possibility to onboard other types of resources, such as research products (data, software), is foreseen by the end of this year.

In addition, in the EOSC-Enhance workplan it is foreseen to automate some of the steps of the onboarding procedure, namely the information gathering and service publishing, but this will not happen before the end of this year.

It is worth mentioning that a cross-project task force on onboarding has been established among the four regional projects (EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Synergy, NI4OS-Europe, EOSC-Nordic) and FAIRsFAIR with the goal of leveraging the experiences within the different projects and harmonizing them as much as possible.

During the TF regular meetings, projects share their own outcomes, such as the document on onboarding delivered by the NI4OS-Europe project (Best practices for on-boarding and related policies⁹), and discuss issues and ideas.

The EOSC-hub project will come to its end at December 31 2020 and its activities, specifically the operation of the onboarding process, will be taken over by a follow-on project which is going to be submitted to the INFRAEOSC-03 call.

A new and more detailed version of these guidelines will be contained in deliverable D7.1 (Guidelines and Recommendations for the technical integration of resources and services into the EOSC), due at month 24 (June 2021).

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3736143>